

Empowering Women in the Cantabrian Canning Industry through Biodiesel Production from Anchovy Waste Valorization

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Abstract

The Cantabrian canning industry plays a crucial role in the regional economy, particularly during the anchovy fishing season from March to June. Thousands of tons of anchovies are captured along the Cantabrian coast during this period, generating employment, primarily for women in the region [1]. However, these employment opportunities are precarious due to predominantly fixed-term contracts and low salaries.

This study aims to enhance the working conditions of women in the Cantabrian canning industry by proposing a biodiesel production model through the valorization of generated anchovy waste, primarily consisting of heads and viscera rich in animal fat. The objective is to provide the possibility of extending women's employment throughout the year, even during off-seasons by freezing the waste.

The biodiesel production process consists of two main stages: oil extraction and transesterification reaction. The extraction involves cooking waste from anchovies, composed of heads and viscera, followed by pressing to obtain the oil [2]. After purifying the oil, transesterification takes place using KOH as a catalyst, resulting in Fatty Acid Methyl Esters (FAME) and glycerol as a byproduct. After transesterification, biodiesel needs to be purified to accomplish with the quality standards [3]. Therefore, this stage will also be studied. In this work, the main operation variables have been studied in both processes to get a high-quality biodiesel suitable for being used as a fuel in the fishing fleet of Cantabria region.

Based on the obtained results, the intention is to design a model to assess the feasibility of implementing an on-site biodiesel manufacturing process in Cantabrian canneries. This approach allows active participation of female workers, promoting their empowerment in the sector, with the produced biodiesel potentially supplying the region's own vessels.

References

- [1] Agirregoikoa, A. El papel predominante de la mujer en la industria conservera (2021) Deia.
- [2] Bonilla-Méndez, J. R. & Hoyos-Concha, J. L., (2018) Métodos extracción, refinación y concentración de aceite de pescado como fuente de ácidos grasos omega-3. *Corpoica Ciencia y Tecnología Agropecuaria*, Volume 19 (3), pages 621-644
- [3] Costa, J. F., Almeida, M. F., Alvim-Ferraz, M. C. M., Dias, J. M, (2013) *Energy Conversion and Management*, Volume 74, pages 17-23.

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